

An Roinn Gnóthaí
Eachtracha agus Trádála
Department of
Foreign Affairs and Trade

Public Consultation on the Development of the Priorities and Policy Programme for Ireland's Presidency of the Council of the European Union 2026

Submission by the

Brexit Institute / Dublin European Law Institute (DELI)

at Dublin City University

An Roinn Gnóthaí Eachtracha agus Trádála
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1. Submission Form

Public Consultation on the Development of the Priorities and Policy Programme for Ireland's Presidency of the Council of the European Union 2026

Mandatory questions	
Name	Brexit Institute / Dublin European Law Institute (DELI)
Organisation (if any)	Dublin City University (DCU)
Date of submission	Friday 12 December 2025
Do you agree to all of the terms set out in this consultation process, including those set out under section 5 and 6?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

Optional questions	
<i>The following questions are asked only to help us understand the range of perspectives received as part of this consultation process.</i>	
Respondent type (i.e. individual, NGO, business, academic, local authority, etc.)	Research centre / Think tank
What is your sector/area of work?	EU Law and policy
What is your connection to the issues you are providing feedback on? For example, are you an expert practitioner, person affected by a policy issue, member of the public with a general interest in the topics, etc.?	The Brexit Institute / DELI has an international, interdisciplinary team of circa 20 experts of EU law and policy, with specialized knowledge and experience in several sectoral policy areas, including economic & affairs and competitiveness, EU governance and institutional matters (enlargement, withdrawal), security and defence, human rights, the rule of law and migration, data protection & AI, and environmental law.
Describe your geographical focus in the context of your submission? For example, rural, urban, national or EU wide.	National and EU-wide

Question 1 – What should Ireland choose as the high-level thematic priorities for its Presidency of the Council in 2026?

Please limit response to a maximum of 500 words.

We think that the following areas should be considered thematic priorities for the Presidency of the Council in 2026:

1. Competitiveness, internal market and economic prosperity
2. Defence and security
3. Trade and economic security
4. Enlargement
5. Fundamental rights, justice and the rule of law (Article 7 TEU procedure)
6. Data protection and digital innovation
7. Green transition and energy security
8. Relationship with the UK

Question 2 – Which particular policy areas and legislative proposals should be a focus of work for the Irish Presidency of the Council in 2026? What should the Irish Presidency aim to achieve in these areas?

Please limit response to a maximum of 500 words.

Several policy areas and corresponding legislative proposals should be prioritized, namely:

1. Competitiveness, Internal Market and Economic Prosperity

Ireland's Council Presidency should focus on implementing the agenda of the Letta and Draghi reports, completing the EU internal market and promoting EU economic competitiveness, with the aim of achieving an **economy that works for people**. Among current legislative initiatives, the EU should **develop the 28th regime for European companies**, particularly for SMEs. It will help remove internal barriers in the single market, advance the digitalisation of corporate operations and reduce the fragmented nature of corporate regulation – enhancing the productivity of European businesses.

Ireland's Council Presidency should also focus on **deepening, consolidating and modernising the Single Market in the areas of telecoms, energy, defence industry and services**. Furthermore, the EU should eventually achieve **financial integration by creating a Savings and Investment Union (SIU)**. Ireland, as a key financial hub, could have a significant role in moving forward among others the *'Market integration package'* for a single **market for financial services**.

Ireland's Council Presidency should also promote the **simplification of the regulatory agenda**, but without resulting in de-regulation. It shall develop funding mechanisms to support **European public goods**. It will be noted that the next EU budget, the 2028-2035 Multi-annual Financial Framework (MFF), is due to be concluded during the Irish Council Presidency, so special attention will need to be **devoted to fiscal and budgetary issues, including the introduction of new own resources and future EU debt issuance**.

2. Defence and Security

Given changes in transatlantic relations, Ireland's Council Presidency should devote attention to the development of a **European defence and technological industrial base**. Moreover, given uncertainties about the future role of NATO, and respecting the neutrality of non-aligned EU member states, efforts should be sustained to develop autonomous military capabilities, as well as improve its existing defence governance structures, by strengthening the EU military committee and military planning and conduct capability (MPCC).

Ireland's Council Presidency will need to maintain a strong focus on security and defence in light of Russia's illegal war of aggression against Ukraine. This includes strengthening the Union's capacity to provide long-term security guarantees to Ukraine and addressing the implications of Article 42(7) TEU, the mutual defence clause, particularly in the context of closer political and security alignment with partner countries.

3. Trade and Economic Security

Ireland's Council Presidency should promote the **conclusion of new trade agreements and the ratification of deals** that the EU has already reached, e.g. with Mercosur. Moreover, it should champion free trade drawing on New Zealand's example (see FIT Partnership, ACCTS, cooperation with CPTPP) in the **interest of EU's competitiveness**. At the same time, Ireland's Council Presidency should combine openness towards trade with a focus on economic security, e.g. by fully implementing the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Screening Regulation, the Anti-Coercion Instrument and the other mechanisms in the EU toolbox.

4. Enlargement

Ireland's Council Presidency should prioritise **EU enlargement as a strategic policy area**, based on a merit-based and differentiated approach. Particular focus could be placed on Montenegro and Albania, while negotiations with Ukraine, Moldova and other Western Balkan candidates continue, alongside work on gradual integration, EU absorption capacity including necessary EU reforms and strict rule-of-law conditionality.

5. Fundamental Rights, Justice and the Rule of Law

Ireland's Council Presidency should seek to advance the Art. 7 TEU procedure on rule of law backsliding in Member States, including with a move to a vote on Art. 7 (2) TEU in the Council, as this allows the EU to show that it is capable of acting in light of rule of law threats from within. Deepening of the relationship with the Council of Europe should also be explored.

6. Data protection and digital innovation

Ireland's Council Presidency should **preserve its data protection framework and enforcement laws**, despite foreign pressures, and start a conversation on the regulation of data centres in the EU, from a cybersecurity, energy, environmental, and technological sovereignty perspective. Securing data centres' capacity in the EU has a strategic value, and contributes to the **objectives of the digital and green transition**.

7. Green transition and energy security

Ireland's Council Presidency should continue the fight against climate change while phasing out of Russian fossil fuels. Ireland's natural endowments place it in a strong position to **lead the development of offshore wind energy**, thereby enhancing **EU energy security and supporting low-carbon economic growth**. Ireland should actively promote the expansion of this sector, advancing offshore wind and other low-carbon technologies, building resilient supply chains with non-EU partners. Ireland is well placed to foster these relationships, supported by its longstanding ties with many developing countries.

8. Relationship with the UK

Given its role as the closest neighbour to the UK (now a former EU Member State after Brexit) Ireland should use the Council Presidency as an opportunity to deepen EU-UK relations, e.g. by concluding the SPS agreement, and other sectoral accords envisaged in the May 2025 EU-UK reset.

Question 3 – How can the work of the Council during the term of the Irish Presidency make the most substantial positive impact for people, businesses and communities across the EU?

Please limit response to a maximum of 500 words.

The Irish Council Presidency would make the most substantial positive impact by focusing on the following areas:

- For **businesses, benefiting the EU's economy and society**, therefore its people and communities:

By pushing for the full implementation of the Letta and Draghi reports, including setting up a **28th regime for innovative companies**, Ireland would position itself as a start-up hub in Europe. A **prominent competitiveness theme** will contribute to keeping the EU economy buoyant, creating or preserving employment, lowering costs, raising living standards, and preserving the global position of the EU.

- For **people, businesses and communities' rights protection**:

Ireland can have a decisive influence on the lives of Europeans if it seeks to advance the **accession of the European Union to the European Convention on Human Rights**. This can be achieved both through policy prioritisation within the Council, as well as through Ireland's membership of the Council of Europe.

- For **people, businesses and communities' understanding of the post-COVID-19 Recovery funding**:

As the Irish Council Presidency will coincide with the **end of the implementation of the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)**, it would be the ideal moment to showcase to the public the **achievements across all EU Member States and in Ireland (projects, reforms and investments)**, illustrating them concretely throughout the six policy pillars supported with EU funding. Such an endeavour would support effectiveness of EU policies and accountability.

Question 4 – How can we best communicate the values and benefits of EU membership to its citizens and create a sense of ownership, amongst citizens, over Ireland's Presidency of the Council of the EU?

Please limit response to a maximum of 500 words.

We have several proposals to ensure **communication on the values and benefits of EU membership to the broader public, namely:**

- Establish an **EU Council Presidency Strategic Engagement Fund** which would allow Ireland to partner with research centres and appropriate think tanks in order to deliver **events in person, online or in hybrid form on specific policy priorities** which draw upon the expertise of the relevant partner organisation during the term of the Irish Council Presidency, in partnership with, or on behalf of the Irish Government.
- Ensure **campaigns, events and social media presence, in partnership with** academic and research communities and civil society actors, e.g. weekly seminars, debates and forums (for example, in cooperation with the Brexit Institute / Dublin European Law Institute).
- Illustrate the **practical benefits of EU membership for Ireland** through a *video series* (focus on one story per county, of something that would not be possible without EU membership).
- Produce a *video series* on the **Resilience and Recovery Facility final phase** with tangible projects financed in Ireland and across the EU.
- Appoint and liaise with **student ambassadors** in each university and school to help communicate the benefits of EU membership to younger generations.

Question 5 – Any other comments

Respondents are welcome to submit additional information alongside Submission Form. However, in such cases, respondents must provide a summary of the additional information under the 'Any other comments' question. This summary should also be limited to a maximum of 500 words.

The Brexit Institute/Dublin European Law Institute, as a leading research centre & think tank for European law and policy in Dublin, remains open to support the Irish Government during its Council Presidency and to cooperate, e.g. by hosting events with the Government and relevant partners, before and during the Irish Council Presidency.

Contact point for this submission

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